

RESEARCH PAPER

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION AND PRELIMINARY EVALUATION OF FOUR BREEDING LINES OF *Brassica Juncea* (MUSTARD SEED) IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

In order to enhance commercial production of mustard seed (*Brassica juncea*) in the tropics, varieties need to be bred that are high yielding, disease resistant and fully adapted to Nigeria's tropical climate. Four distinct breeding lines of *B. juncea* obtained from an introduced accession of Indian origin were planted out in a randomized complete block design and characterized for plant height, number of seeds per pod, pod length, leaf length, leaf width, petiole length, 1000-seed weight, and days to first flowering. Five qualitative traits including seed coat color, stem pigmentation, leaf shape, stem pubescence, and susceptibility to lodging were also observed. Analysis of variance revealed significant differences among the breeding lines for the morphological characters studied. High variation was observed for plant height, days to first flowering, leaf length and width, and number of seeds per pod. Pod length, number of branches, seed weight and petiole length exhibited the least variation. Generally, low correlation was observed among different traits but a number of characters were observed to be significantly correlated with one another, indicating some level of association among the traits studied. Principal component analysis resulted in the first two components with Eigen value greater than 1 accounting for 78% of the total variation. Further expansion of the *B. juncea* gene pool through introduction of exotic genotypes, mutation breeding and hybridization will increase the variation available to breeders for developing desired genotypes that will adapt optimally to the tropical environment.

KEYWORDS: mustard, *Brassica juncea*, morphological variation, selection, breeding

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INTRODUCTION

Brassica juncea is an amphidiploid with *Brassica nigra* (L.) Koch ($2n = 16$) and *Brassica rapa* L. ($2n = 20$) as parents. Several regions in western and central Asia have been assumed to be the Centre of origin of *Brassica juncea*. It has been cultivated in Asia and Europe for thousands of years for its leaves and seeds. Variations are greatest in China (Proata). The brassica genus contains many agronomical important crop species with a wide range of adaptation for cultivation under varied agro climatic conditions (Robert et al., 2009). Brown mustard has been reported to be grown as a leafy vegetable in West and southern Africa, known as 'laulau' in Nigeria, 'mpiru' in Malawi and 'tsunga' in Zimbabwe (Proata).

In Africa and many parts of Asia, the leaves are eaten as a vegetable, young tender leaves, called 'mustard greens' are used in salads, mixed with other salad greens. It is also used as forage and medicinally. Mustard oil is one of the major edible oils in Bangladesh, India and Pakistan, appreciated for its special taste and pungency (Proata). However mustard in Nigeria has been used for medicinal purposes as anti-poison by local herbal practitioners but

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they depend on imported seeds by pilgrims from the holy land, Jerusalem for their supply. Plant germplasm is vital in generating new types having desired traits that help increase food production thus improve the level of human nutrition (Rabbani *et al.*, 1999). The value of a germplasm collection depends not only on the number of accessions it contains, but also upon the diversity present in these accessions (Ren *et al.*, 1995).

According to Tomooka (1991), the evaluation of diversity is important to know the source of genes for particular trait within the available germplasm and promotes the efficient use of genetic variation in establishing a breeding programme. There is not a clear association between genetic distance and taxonomic classification within the Brassicaceae (Gomez-Campo and Prakash, 1999; Warwick *et al.*, 2000). For an efficient breeding program, information concerning the extent and nature of genetic diversity within a crop species is useful for characterizing individual accessions and cultivars in the selection of parents for hybridization (Rabbani *et al.*, 1998). Also attempts have been made at the molecular level to understand genetic diversity by estimating relatedness among crop germplasm in brassica crops, using RAPD (Chuang *et al.* 2004; Cartea *et al.* 2005).

Mutual association of plant characters which is determined by correlation co-efficient is useful for indirect selection. Khayat *et al.*, (2012) and Hasan *et al.*, 2015 found positive direct effect of 1000-seed weight and days to maturity on yield in mustard. Sinha *et al.*, (2001) also reported that plant height had a negative direct effect on yield per plant. Genetic variability studies are important in the selection of parents for hybridization and once genetic variability has been ascertained in a crop, improvement is possible through the use of appropriate selection method (Chaudhary and Singh, 1982).

Planned plant introduction and collection therefore becomes inevitable whenever the genetic base of a germplasm becomes narrow for important desirable traits. However the genetic diversity and relationship among selected mustard accessions from an introduced seed lot in Nigeria has not been studied so far. This study was carried out as a prelude to identify genetically diverse and agronomical superior accessions that will best adapt to our environment and can also be used as genitors in active breeding programme geared towards producing varieties that will adapt and give optimum yield in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Study was carried out at NIHORT-National Horticultural Research Institute, Ibadan, Nigeria from August to November 2010. Seedlings of the four lines (T1, T2, T3, T4) selected from an introduced *B. juncea* accession were raised in deep nursery trays filled with fertile sandy-loam soil. Transplanting was done four weeks after sowing, i.e. at 3 - 4 leaf stage. The four lines were planted out in a randomized complete block design with three replicates. Plot size was 2m x 2m. A plant spacing of 0.5m x 0.5m was maintained. Consequently, each experimental plot consisted of 9 individual plants per plot, excluding the border plants. Best agronomic practices were observed throughout the duration of the study.

Morphological characterization was based on 9 quantitative characters, namely, number of branches (NB), days to 50% flowering (D50%F), plant height (PH), leaf length (LL), leaf width (LW), petiole length (PL), length of pod (LP), number of seeds per pod (NSP), 1000 seed weight (1000SW). Seven qualitative traits evaluated are leaf shape, leaf margin, leaf pubescence, stem pubescence, stem pigmentation, seed color and lodging score. Five plants were sampled per plot for data collection for each breeding line. Using the statistical analysis program SAS 2000, the data was subjected to analysis of variance, and also used to derive descriptive statistics for the quantitative characters. Simple correlation coefficient between all pairs of characters was then calculated using SAS 2000. In order to identify the patterns of morphological variation, (PCA) was conducted. Those PCs with Eigen values greater than one were selected as proposed by Jeffers (1967). Correlations between the original traits and the respective PCs were calculated. Qualitative trait observations were made using a modified descriptor list for the present study.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The range of variation observed among the accessions for nine agro-morphological descriptors is presented in Table 1. The analysis of variance revealed significant differences between the accessions for 7 of the 9 quantitative characters, with only differences in number of branches (NB) and length of pod (LP) showing no significance. Plant height had the highest range (103.6) followed by days to 50% flowering (D50%), while number of branches (NB) and Petiole Length (PL) both recorded the lowest ranges (1.0). The highest levels of variation were observed for plant height, days to 50% flowering (D50F), leaf length (LL), number of seeds per pod (NSP) and leaf width (LW), while the lowest levels of variability were observed for length of pod (LP), number of branches (NB), and 1000 seed weight (1000SW). The number of days from sowing to flowering ranged from 30 days for T1 to 80 days for T3 and T4. Also the height of the observed accessions varied with T1 having the shortest height of 44.4cm to T3 and T4 with average height of 148cm. Leaf size at flowering stage showed a great deal of variability with varying lengths from 3.9cm in T1 to 25.9cm in T2, confirming the report of Rabbani *et al.*, 1999, of high variability in leaf sizes of mustard. Selections in favor of the accessions with bigger leaf can be lead to developing bigger leafed varieties of mustard that can be used for fodder and vegetable purposes. Also selection for plants that are dwarf or of average height in nature may be employed in breeding for improved varieties that are resistant to lodging, since mustard varieties with moderate plant height, branch point, lower gravity center of plant and compact plant architecture possess high lodging resistance (CHEN Xin-Jun *et al.*, 2007). Low variability for number of branches/plant as observed in this study is in line with the report of Rabbani *et al.*, 1999 and will restrict the scope of selection for these traits in the present germplasm collection but genes for these traits may be exploited by other means like mutation breeding. The corresponding high CVs observed for NB and LP (18.2 and 13.1, respectively) may indicate the existence of individual outlier values in the sampled plants.

Table 2 shows the variation observed for the 7 qualitative traits in this study. It was observed that leaf margin had a relationship with leaf and stem pubescence, such that the two breeding lines with entire leaf margins (T1 and T2) exhibited hairiness on neither leaves nor stems, while T3 and T4 (with serrate margins) had hairs on both leaves and stems. No other obvious relationship was observed with the other traits. Line T3 only differed from T4 in having a light reddish-purple pigmentation on its stems and leaf veins. Seed color varied considerably among the four breeding lines studied, ranging from grey in T1, to three distinct shades of brown for T2 (dark brown), T3 (brown) and T4 (light brown).

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Correlation among the various morphological characters is presented in (Table 3). Some of the traits showed high and significant correlation among the four mustard accessions under study (Table 1). Rabbani *et al.*, 1998, reported high positive correlation between bolting and flowering time, leaf size and plant height of mustard genotypes. Measurement of some related traits were also significantly correlated with one another in this study. Leaf length, leaf width, petiole length, days to 50% flowering all showed high positive association with plant height ($r < 0.50$) at flowering. Negative correlation of yield with plant height and plant branches have been observed and reported by researchers (Hasan *et al.*, 2015; Basalma, 2011; Sinha *et al.*, 2001). Caradus *et al.*, (1989) reported the tendency of large leaves and tall height cultivars to be late flowering in white clover. Highly significant correlation has been reported between leaf length, days to bud formation and days to first flowering by Kennard *et al.*, (1994) in *B.oleracea*. Similarly, leaf width, petiole length and days to first flowering was highly correlated with leaf length ($r < 0.50$). Leaf width also showed strong positive correlation with petiole length and days to first flowering ($r < 0.50$). 1000 seed weight showed very poor correlation with the other morphological characters. The high positive correlation observed among some traits in this study may be as a result of the control and influence of a particular gene on the traits under consideration.

Principal component analysis

The PCA was used to eliminate redundancy in the data set. Two principal components (PC 1) and (PC 2) accounted for most of the variability observed among the four mustard collections from India (Table 4). PC 1 accounted for 56.72% of the morphological variation and was loaded on petiole length (PL), plant height (PH), leaf length (LL),

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days to 50% flowering (D50%F), length of pod (LP), number of branches (NB), days to 50% flowering (D50%F) while PC2 accounted for 20.92% of the variation and was loaded on total number of 1000 seed weight (1000SW), number of branches (NB), number of seeds per pod (NSP). Eigen value associated with each principle out of the six PCA decreased gradually and stopped at 0.210 and 0.090 respectively.

CONCLUSION

From the results obtained, the four breeding lines selected from the introduced seed lot have displayed considerable morphological variation that can be harnessed to improve and adapt this valuable crop to our tropical environment. Possible aspects of breeding interest will be early maturity, seed color and weight, and resistance to lodging. The results also indicate the potential for hybrid development. However, further investigations on the action and inheritance pattern of traits of agronomic interest need to be elucidated to enhance their usefulness in future mustard improvement programmes.

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Table 1. Statistical description and ANOVA of nine quantitative characters in four selections of *B. juncea*.

Characters	Mean	SD	Min	Max	CV(%)	Variance	F-Value	LSD
Length of pod	3.18	0.37	2.50	3.50	13.1	0.65	0.610	0.83
Number of seeds	10.92	3.58	5.00	17.00	13.4	7.97	0.02	4.07
Plant height	105.92	34.79	41.40	148.00	6.5	92.14	<0.001	13.63
Number of branches	2.58	0.51	2.00	3.00	18.2	1.38	0.34	0.94
Length of leaf	14.02	6.77	3.90	25.90	15.4	33.04	<0.001	4.32
Leaf width	9.33	4.31	2.00	14.00	11.7	50.40	<0.001	2.18
Petiole length	6.20	2.33	2.20	8.10	6.7	112.82	<0.001	0.83
Days to 50% flowering	65.00	20.27	30.00	80.00	1.9	965.25	<0.001	2.49
1000 Seed weight	3.49	1.25	1.50	4.83	7.0	92.93	<0.001	0.49

Table 2. Variation of seven qualitative characters in four selections of *B. juncea*.

Breeding line	Leaf shape	Leaf margin	Leaf pubescence	Stem pubescence	Stem pigmentation	Seed color	Lodging score*
T1	Spathulate	Entire	Absent	Absent	Absent	Grey	5
T2	Round	Entire	Absent	Absent	Absent	Dark brown	7
T3	Ovate	Serrate	Present	Present	Purple	Brown	1
T4	Ovate	Serrate	Present	Present	Absent	Light brown	3

*1 =no plants lodged on entire plot; 3 =¼ of the plants lodged; 5: ½ of the plants lodged; 7 =¾ of the plants lodged; 9 =all plants lodged

Table 3. Correlation coefficient between 9 quantitative traits of mustard accessions

	LP	NSP	PH	NB	LL	LW	PL	D50%F	1000SW
LP	1.00000								
NS	-0.16060	1.00000							
PH	-0.43488	0.01647	1.00000						
NB	-0.61838	-0.36583	0.44413	1.00000					
LL	-0.47891	-0.08923	0.91420	0.50027	1.00000				
CS	-0.28620	0.27412	0.88170	0.17294	0.86414	1.00000			
PL	-0.51102	0.27412	0.93575	0.30364	0.88248	0.95169	1.00000		
50%F	-0.44799	0.39469	0.85657	0.22644	0.77116	0.90401	0.95855	1.00000	
1000SW	-0.20993	-0.27950	0.30185	0.48102	0.34196	0.16403	0.18766	0.00906	1.00000

Where LP = Length of pod , NSP = Number of seeds per pod , PH = Plant height, NB = Number of branches, LL = Leaf length, LW = Leaf width, PL = Petiole length, D50%F = Days to 50% flowering, 1000SW = 1000 seed weight.

Table 4. Eigenvector (“Weight”) and Eigen value (“Load”) of the correlation matrix and their contribution to total variation of mustard germplasm collections.

Descriptor variables	PC 1	PC 2
%1000SW	-0.137	0.48663
NB	-0.21733	0.53267
CS	-0.40297	-0.18636
50%F	-0.4026	-0.26188
PH	-0.42295	0.01981
LL	-0.41461	0.10311
LP	0.2612	-0.17397
NSP	-0.06208	-0.55955
PL	-0.43204	-0.14752
Eigen value	5.104	1.883
Proportion %	56.72	20.92

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